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ABSTRACT

Street vending was declared illegal by an Act of parliament in Zambia in 1992 because of the increase in negative outcomes including pickpocketing, worsening public hygiene and order, exacerbating the spread of diseases, tax evasion, and environmental pollution. Despite the numerous negative outcomes of street vending, it is undoubtedly the largest creator of informal jobs, both for skilled and unskilled immigrants and citizens. Despite many suggestions, strategies and efforts of many stakeholders and researchers to find a lasting solution to street vending in Zambia, the vendors are still trading on the undesignated streets. The aim of this research was therefore to explore the views and experiences of the participants on the sustainable panaceas for street vending in Ndola. The failure of the Local Authorities (LAs) in Zambia to permanently evict street vendors from trading in the undesignated places, despite their various interventions and resources committed, necessitated this research. Researchers conducted legal analysis to examine the current laws against street vending and found lacunas that need to be addressed. Qualitative research methodology and phenomenology design employed to explore the lived experiences of the participants. A conceptual framework for negotiated and tailored vendors' access to rights claims and trading spaces in urban areas was adopted for this research. Key findings of the research reveals the need for the engineers under the planning department to redesign the town and markets to promote not only market access but also to accommodate population growth. There is also

inconsistent enforcement of the law by each new political party in power, while vendors see street vending as a source of household (HH) livelihood due to high unemployment levels. Furthermore, it was found that there are allegations of unreasonable use of force by some LA security officers during crackdowns. In addition, a wide range of sustainable panaceas for street vending noted by the respondents, together with some paradoxical tensions be examined by authorities and stakeholders. The exercise to remove street vendors from the streets resulted in increased alleged corrupt practices by some law enforcement officers. The study concludes by clearly stating the pertinent issues that need to be considered including revisiting the current law on street vending with a view to regulating street vending and finding a win-win strategy to amend the law, coming up with measures to allocate a timeframe for street vending and the issuance of trading permits. Furthermore, consideration should be made to formulate tax system (e.g. presumptive tax) for street vending, and reintroduce Hawkers licenses that was abolished. This could be done by the Ndola City Council Councilors in liaison with the Central Government, by coming up with a bye law specially dealing with the above, or, in the alternative and better still, the Local Government Act (2019) itself could be amended, or indeed, a Statutory Instrument (SI) could be issued by the Minister with a view to incorporating into the law the foregoing matters. In addition, markets need to be redesigned to increase both capacity and resolve the unfair trader-buyer market access challenge, address all the paradoxical tensions noted, and improve hygiene and sanitary facilities in market places.

Keywords: Street vendors, vending, sustainable panaceas, informal economy, environmental pollution

INTRODUCTION

Street vending is a global phenomenon that in some developed countries, is no longer viewed as a public nuisance because of the public health measures put in place. The various social, economic, and political factors of different countries shape the historical context of street vending. This global phenomenon can be traced back to periods of early urbanization through the 21st century, where globalization has largely influenced the emergency of street vending in most African countries. Since time immemorial, Zambia has also grappled with the challenge of street vending. Chileshe and Moonga (2017) argued that increased urbanization, high rates of poverty in Zambian cities, and a dearth of suitable official sector job prospects have forced some citizens to turn to the informal sector in order to make a living. Zambia's declining industrial sector in the wake of trade liberalization and privatization in the early 1990s is largely responsible for the country's overall economic downturn, which is also strongly linked to the country's emerging informal economy (Resnick, 2018). According to Ndhlovu (2011), street vending is among the informal livelihoods that many impoverished and jobless Zambians rely on. However, street vending presents a dichotomous situation as there are merits and demerits that come with it leading to endless controversies (Chileshe, 2020).

A study conducted by Hansen (2004) on Zambia gives a foundation to the issue of street vending and the mediations that the administration has implemented so far. In the last part of the 1990s, Zambia developed another ultra-modern day market in the capital city of Lusaka to cater for street vendors; the construction of the market was done before the migration of all street vendors who used to maintain their day-to-day business in the space distributed for the new market foundation. At first, the street vendors battled to be allocated stores in the new market. However, most street vendors went to the streets again as the expenses for working in the new privately operated market were excessively high for most sellers to manage (Hansen & Vaa 2004). Thus,

those that could stand to pay took possession of the stores, and those that couldn't kept trading on the street roads.

In 1999, a mission of expulsion of street vendors from the central business district of Lusaka to occupy formal markets was championed by local authorities (LA). However, it was not until 2002 that LA, with help from the police, achieved its mission to remove street vendors from the streets. Hansen (2004) claimed that the policemen were positioned in high-density areas of Lusaka for a surprisingly long time to guarantee that street vendors didn't get back into the city. This mission was persuaded by the need to establish a conducive environment, advance better wellbeing, and expand security for the city populace and vendors (Hansen, 2004). The same approach to removing street vendors was taken last year, around January 2023, when the New Dawn President, Hichilema Hakainde, issued a presidential directive to remove all street vendors from selling in the streets. As of today, most street vendors are back on the same streets where they were evicted. We argue that evicting street vendors from the streets is not a guarantee of a sustainable solution in Zambia. We further argue that although there are several studies conducted on this subject globally, a gap exists on sustainable panaceas for street vending, contextualized in African countries. Furthermore, it is unknown which recommendations put forward by the various researchers have been successfully implemented by the authorities. Therefore, there is a need for governments to evaluate successful and unsuccessful recommendations implemented to address the problem of street vending.

Despite the numerous vices of street vending, it is undoubtedly the largest creator of informal jobs, both for skilled and unskilled immigrants and citizens. It is estimated that over two billion people work in the informal sector, or about 60% of the world's total employed population (ILO, 2022). In Zambia, the annual labor force survey report (2022), "Of the 3,273,123, employed

persons, 63.5 percent were in the informal economy while 36.5 percent were in the formal economy” (p.45).

In this study, researchers attempted to answer the research question, *How do participants describe sustainable panaceas for street vending in Zambia?* Furthermore, the research problem that was addressed in this study is that although the local authorities in Zambia have on several occasions removed street vendors from trading in the streets, the exercise has not yielded the desired results over time. Street vendors are determined to continue trading in the undesignated places because of economic reasons (Matamanda et al., 2023). In addition, in Maseru, many residents are forced to turn to street hawking due to the city's socioeconomic problems, which include high unemployment, rising poverty rates, and declining living standards (World Bank, 2019). In various cities, there are cycles whereby local government officials first tolerate, then control, and finally remove street vendors in response to demands related to urban management, election cycles, and economic trends (Ndhlovu, 2011). These inconsistencies noted in the different political parties that come into power, tend to defeat the purpose of enacting the law against street vending in Zambia. In this regard, the researcher focused on the following objectives in this study:

1. To explore the lived experiences of street vendors in Ndola.
2. To explore the experiences of decision-makers in addressing street vending.
3. To find out the possible lasting solutions to street vending in Ndola.

The limitations of the research included untimely crackdowns by LA security officers during data collection and the sensitive nature of the topic, where some street vendors felt that the data collectors were actually secret service officials. The researchers overcame the aforementioned limitations by ensuring only a few interviews were planned and conducted per day, and by wearing university identification cards in the field.

The final part of this paper focuses on the literature reviewed, conceptual framework, discussion of findings, conclusion, recommendations, and areas for future research and policy implications have also been highlighted.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A synthesis of the literature review was carried out by the researchers to derive themes from the sources. We argue that although there are several studies conducted on this subject globally, it is unknown which recommendations put forward by the researchers have been successfully implemented by the authorities in Africa and in particular, Zambia. For example, Chileshe (2020) noted that some of the major suggestions to address street vending include:

- No buyers, no vendors: Principle of Collective responsibility
- Strengthen and enforce laws against street vending or regulation
- Provide jobs for street vendors
- Provide environmental education to street vendors
- Provide adequate trading places
- Training and regulation
- Space and time allocation for street vending
- Issue street vending licenses (Chileshe, 2020).

Despite all these suggestions, the Local Authorities in Zambia are yet to find a lasting solution to street vending because vendors are still trading in the undesignated streets.

The following are the themes that emerged from the synthesis of literature reviewed and the Zambian legal analysis on street vending.

Perpetual Street Vending

A synthesis of the literature review clearly indicated that although the law against street vending is clear in many countries that do not support legalizing it, street vendors' perpetual trading in the streets has continued. As Matamanda et al. (2023, p. 6) found in their study from interviewing one of the street vendors, selling of fruits was justified by several vendors who pointed out that “selling fruits makes it possible to access claim rights to use and appropriation of the streets as the use of wheelbarrows, carts, or small tables does not take much space and also allows me to be mobile and evade the authorities.” The existing research clearly shows that street vendors have devised strategies to evade the authorities and are committed to doing so at the expense of being penalized. For example, some of the street vendors sell goods that are easy to move and evade authorities as and when LA operations are conducted to evict them (Matamanda et al., 2023, p. 6). In addition, some street vendors not only sell goods on behalf of shop owners but also have a mutual relationship where their goods are securely stored in the shops whenever authorities implement a crackdown. For example, Yemmafouo (2018) argued that vendors procure goods from suppliers on credit because of the commercial or familial relationship that links them. Furthermore, this kind of relationship has been described as a fidelity alliance, which ensures the supplier's control over the street seller and perpetuates street vending (Yemmafouo, 2018). On the contrary, in most countries in Africa, authorities disparage and despise street vending to the extent that it is outright criminalized (WIEGO, 2019). In this regard, there is a perpetual antagonistic relationship between street vendors and the authorities. It can be argued that the motivations of street vendors being defiant to the law of the land have not been considered by authorities because of the illegal nature of their business activity. As long as street vending is illegal, it offers no opportunity for stakeholder dialogue. To effectively address this issue, it is imperative to critically examine what constitutes this defiant behavior of street vendors against the prevailing law because it is unclear how other scholars and researchers have addressed these tensions with tangible results.

Perpetual tensions and allegations of corruption.

Tensions between street vendors and the authorities arise not only because of the crackdown operations but also because of corruption. Some local authority officers tend to engage in all forms of corruption during the crackdown on street vendors. When authorities engage in negotiations with street vendors, most often than not, it can lead to corruption and patronage systems (Pulliat et al., 2023). The best strategy employed by African governments to address the issue of street vending is usually to engage in crackdowns on street vending, which tends to not only worsen the abuses but also increase government corruption and the general lack of accountability (WIEGO, 2019). As a result, there are perpetual tensions and corruption cases where street vendors are evicted from accessing public spaces.

The Economic Reasons of Street Vending

The majority of people in developing countries (DCs) resort to street vending as a way to make a living. Anja and Zhang (2023) claimed that rising unemployment levels, the desire for unrestrained autonomy, low initial investment requirements, easy market entry, social connections, and the quest to boost meager wages constitute major factors for people engaging in street vending. In recent years, it has been noted that street vending is not only for the poor and uneducated people but also the well-to-do and educated ones, largely because of the increasing levels of urban unemployment as a result of the impact of COVID-19, the global financial crisis, and the deteriorating economic variables of most countries (Al-Jundi et al., 2022; WIEGO, 2019). Al-Jundi et al. (2022) argued that the unemployment rate is obviously going to remain high in DCs as compared to developed countries due to low income per capita because the ratio of their investment to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is lower. However, the illegal nature of street vending does not exclude street vendors from paying taxes for doing business, and yet governments do not consider this huge source of potential revenue. On the contrary, street vending is problematic and leads to

numerous vices, including conflicts and sometimes violence. Unlicensed street vendors employ children who have been accused of counterfeiting and illicit drug trading in their quest to reducing poverty and unemployment (Al-Jundi et al., 2022).

Strategic Spaces

Despite street vending compromising the aesthetics of the CBD, street vendors focus on thriving businesses as they also seek to strategically position their goods where there is high traffic of passersby. The issue of market access by street vendors has been a huge concern that authorities pay a deaf ear to because of the illegal nature of the business. There are several issues that arise because of regulatory frameworks that prohibit street vendors from accessing public spaces and incomes for groups and poor people (Pulliat et al., 2023). Therefore, the unfavorable conditions for possible dialogue to find a lasting solution to street vending between street vendors and authorities are far-fetched (Matamanda et al., 2023). On one hand, street vendors have no right to access strategic spaces in public as long as the law for that particular country does not allow it. On the other hand, Sustainable Development Goals numbers eight (8) and eleven (11) promote sustainable economic growth and inclusiveness, making cities inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable, respectively (UN DESA, 2023). We argue that promoting inclusiveness in accessing public spaces without capturing informal actors such as street vendors is a missed opportunity in many countries.

Legalized Vending Sites

There are countries with success stories of regulated street vending (Shula, 2023). In urban communities like New York City and Los Angeles, selling on the streets is managed through permits and assigned vending zones. This takes into consideration a controlled extension of street vending while guaranteeing consistency with wellbeing and security standards. Merchants are

expected to adhere to and comply with explicit regulations, finding some kind of harmony between vendors and order. Japan's "yatai," or mobile food shop stands, have a long practice of sanctioned selling in the streets. These mobile food shop stands are regulated in view of wellbeing and cleanliness guidelines while safeguarding the social experience, and mobile food shop stands are customary for local people and vacationers. A few European urban communities, like Amsterdam and Barcelona, have assigned street vending zones where merchants can legitimately work. Guidelines guarantee the protection of public spaces while permitting merchants to add to the neighborhood, economy, and culture. Chinese urban communities like Shanghai and Beijing have assigned street vending regions and night markets where merchants can legitimately work. While regulators control these regions with strict adherence to standards, the government values the significant role of street vending as a component of the social and financial aspects of the locals, keeping harmony between control and liveliness. By creating Town Vending Committees and designated vending zones in India, the Street Vendors Act of 2014 offers a legislative framework to control street vending. According to studies, the act supports urban peace and vendor rights, although it is difficult to implement and strike a balance between the interests of the public and vendors (Peimani & Kamalipour, 2022). To assist street vendors, Bogotá in Colombia has put in place formal market areas, training programs, and microloans. Vendors continue to face operational expenses and accessibility challenges in spite of these initiatives (Peimani & Kamalipour, 2022).

It can be argued that in the aforementioned countries where street vending is legalized, informal traders enjoy protection from authorities, participate in local authority planning, and cities promote the cultural identity of their respective countries. A paradigm shift is required not to always think of criminalizing street vending and other people accessing urban spaces by local authority planners in order to put up measures to address demand-side factors (Solidum, 2023, as cited in Igudia, 2020).

Legal Analysis of the Zambian Law

As regards the law on street vending in Zambia, the Local Government Act No. 2 of 2019 is the main law. This is the new law in the sense that it repeals and replaces the Local Government Act, 1991. The 1991 Act, just like the 2019 Act, is now the enabling law vis-à-vis the management of municipalities countrywide. Under both laws, the Minister of Local Government and Housing (now called the Minister of Local Government and Rural Development) has the power by SI to make regulations for any purpose. Under the same token, a LA is also empowered to make by-laws or standing orders. Whereas an SI applies throughout the country, by-laws or standing orders only apply within the district where the by-laws or standing orders are made. A perusal of both the repealed Local Government Act and the one that is in force shows that the law does not cut down on street vending and, in particular, matters connected thereto, such as the allocation of a timeframe for street vending and the issuance of trading permits. Rather, what the law requires is to prohibit street vending altogether on account of the many menaces associated with it. In view of the menaces that were deemed to be associated with street vending, which include the following, there was, in the central government's view, a need to enhance the law:

- (a) Indiscriminate disposal of solid waste;
- (b) Blocking of drainages;
- (c) Erection of makeshift stores and booths;
- (d) Preparation and selling of foodstuffs in an unsafe environment;
- (e) Illegal sale of intoxicating substances, including liquor;
- (f) Non-payment of council levies; and

(g) Deterioration of public health and safety standards. (Parliament, n.d.).

Thus, in response to the foregoing, the then Minister aforesaid added stringent provisions to the SI that dealt with street vending and matters related thereto. This was done through the Street Vending and Nuisances Regulations, 2018 (Parliament, n.d.). In this case, the Minister came up with the Local Government (Street Vending and Nuisances) (Amendment) Regulations, 2018. It follows that this is the law that all LAs in the country, including the Ndola City Council, the LA under consideration herein, have lately been invoking following a directive from the central government to remove street vendors from the street and other undesignated trading places. It is worth noting that the said SI of 2018 simply amends the Local Government (Street Vending and Nuisances) Regulations, 1992, and the said 2018 Regulations are thus to be read as one with the 1992 Regulations. Thus, the 2018 Regulations prescribe many offenses associated with the topic under consideration. These include the following offenses, inter alia:

- a. Throwing a liter on, or along, a street or prescribed road
- b. Sale of local produce in any street or in a public place other than a market established by the council, except with the permission of the councils
 - i. Food
 - ii. Any other item or product...
- c. Disposing or allowing to accumulate or keeping upon any premises any dirty, filthy, rubbish, or offensive matter or matter likely to become offensive...
- d. Conduct street business or sell ready meals in a van or other conveyances that are not licensed... (The Local Government (Street Vending and Nuisances) (Amendment) Regulations, 2018).

In terms of penalties for the above offenses and others not listed, they are prescribed in Penalty Fee Units, and they range from 333.33 Fee Units for the offense associated with spitting

or vomiting on or alongside streets or roads as the lowest penalty to the maximum of 2,500.00 Fee Units for many offenses, for example, the foregoing offense of street business or selling ready meals in a van, etc. The penalties are high in view of the provisions under the Fees and Fines (Fee and Penalty Unit Value) (Amendment) Regulations, 2015, made by the Minister of Finance pursuant to the Fees and Fines Act, 1994. The value of a penalty unit is thirty ngwee. By way of example, a person found guilty of street business or selling ready meals in a van, etc., will have to pay 2,500.00 fee units, which comes to K750 in actual monetary terms, or serve a term of imprisonment as the sitting magistrate would deem fit. The foregoing proposition is premised on the assumption that since the Local Government (Street Vending and Nuisances) Regulations, 1992, and the 2018 Regulations, when read together, only provide a fine, the court, in cases where the convict is not able to pay the fine, uses its discretion to impose a sentence reasonable in the circumstances. The Criminal Procedure Code, 1934, under Section 7 thereof, is thus instructive. It enacts, inter alia, that:

Subject to the other provisions of this Code, a subordinate court of the first, second, or third class may try any offense under the Penal Code or any other written law and may pass any sentence or make any other order authorized by the Penal Code or any other written law. The authors opine thus that the fact that courts want to assist in curbing the offenses associated with street vending, its rate of recurrence, and also the fact that street vendors want to only break the law, inter alia, are some of the matters that courts consider when arriving at an appropriate sentence.

The authors further opine that the law as regards dealing with street vending is okay, in particular the penalties associated with it; however, the law needs attention to allow for regulated street vending that also takes into account security, hygiene, payment of applicable council levies and fees, inter alia, for purposes of attainment of much-desired economic growth and eradication of poverty in the country, especially among the citizens that are not able to, due to one reason or

another, find formal employment, be it in government or the private sector. The foregoing could be attained by way of the Ndola City Council Councilors in liaison with the Central Government coming up with a bye law specially dealing with the above, or in the alternative and better still, the Local Government Act (2019) itself could be amended, or indeed, a Statutory Instrument (SI) could be issued by the Minister so as to incorporate into the law the above matters.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Researchers adopted the framework for negotiated and tailored vendors' access to rights claims and trading spaces in urban areas. The framework draws upon principles of urban planning, community engagement, and inclusive governance. In this research, three key elements of the framework were examined, which included the lived experiences of street vendors, planners, and policymakers, as well as science, research, and development focusing on sustainability. The aforementioned key elements of the conceptual framework helped the researchers provide a theoretical lens through which this research was undertaken to derive the meaning of the complexities inherent in this global phenomenon. In this regard, the researcher examined the interconnectedness of the three key elements in Figure 1 triad as suggested by Matamanda et al. (2023) as follows:

- Investigation of existing lived experiences and constraints for and by street vendors in Ndola.
- Critical examination and gap analysis of legislative and policy frameworks in support of or against street vending in Zambia.
- Gap analysis and examination of street vendor decisions, area and physical siting of conducting business, type and model design of vending structures and building plans,

format and display table forms and types, as well as vending structure development materials utilized, for example, wood, plastics, polythene, and so on.

- A thematic analysis technique to generate new ideas on vending issues and paradoxical tensions between street vendors and authorities with a focus on sustainability issues.

Figure 1

Framework for negotiated and tailored vendors’ access to rights claims and trading spaces in urban areas.

Source: Matamanda et al. (2023)

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research methodology was adopted in this research because of the nature of the research problem, which required an in-depth inquiry. Furthermore, researchers applied phenomenological design to explore street vending, which is a global phenomenon. Three (3) in-depth interviews were conducted with four (4) key informants from local authorities and one (1) in-depth interview with one (1) subject matter expert from the Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA), five (5) shop owners, and twenty (20) street vendors participated in the in-depth interviews. Purposive sampling technique was employed in this research, where only street vendors who have experienced local authority crackdown operations on street vending were interviewed, and only key informants who were subject matter experts from the government participated. The researchers employed a thematic analysis approach to analyze qualitative data collected using semi-structured interviews. Six steps to thematic analysis, as coined by Braun and Clarke (2006) was employed. Furthermore, the concept of trustworthiness was employed in this research to guarantee the reliability and validity of the qualitative findings where member checking was conducted during the data collection process as well as after the report was generated. Furthermore, researchers ensured that the interpretations and conclusions resonated with the experiences of the participants. Data triangulation (method and data source triangulation), adherence to the research process, and data analysis procedures were followed, confirming the findings with the existing research on this global phenomenon.

FINDINGS

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Figure 2

Gender

Note. In this research, there were 47% females and 53% males, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3

Age Range

Note. Figure 3 shows that 43% (the majority) of the respondents were 42 years of age and older.

It is evident from Figure 3 that most street vendors have family responsibilities.

Figure 4

Level of Education Attained

Note. Figure 4 shows that 47% (the majority) of the respondents have completed secondary school education and 27% have never attained any education level. 23% have attained tertiary education, while only 3% (the lowest) have attained primary education. It is clear from Figure 4 that the majority of the respondents do not have the skills to sustain themselves. Furthermore, those who have a skill are engaging in street vending as a form of informal employment.

Figure 5

Level of Education Qualification

Note. Figure 5 shows that 73% (the highest) of the respondents have never attained any educational qualifications, while only 3% (the lowest) have attained diploma level. It is clear from Figure 5 that most of the street vendors have no skills that they can use to sustain themselves.

Figure 6

Nature of Business

Note. Figure 6 shows that 17% and 26% of street vendors engage in the vegetable and fruit business, for a combined total of 43% (the highest). According to LA officials in Ndola, fruits and vegetable sellers generate the highest municipal solid waste.

Experiences of Street Vendors in Ndola

Inconsistent Enforcement of the Law

Inconsistencies in the enforcement of the law on street vending by each political party that comes into power have been noted as one of the major challenges faced not only by law enforcers but also by street vendors. We argue that there are inconsistencies in the enforcement of the law by different political parties in power based on their development agenda. From the time of Movement for Multi-Party Democracy in 1991 to the current party in power-United Party for National Development (UPND) it can be observed below:

- MMD-Focused on Liberalism/multi-partism

- PF-Focused on Pro-poor policies
- UPND-The focus is mainly Economic reconstruction, diplomacy and expansion

One Street Vendor (SV) narrated that “each government comes in with their own policies, which change every time.” Furthermore, another respondent was quick to add that “street vending is political because policies fluctuate; today they say yes, you can trade, and tomorrow another leadership says no, you cannot.” The question that begs answering is: does political interference always override the rule of law? The fact that street sales and purchases continue to occur indicates a lack of enforcement of these SIs. To stop street vending, there must be a strong political will, just like for many other unlawful activities occurring in city precincts (Chileshe & Moonga, 2019). From the findings of this study, it seems that the rule of law is not applicable when political interference is at play. The experience of street vendors with different political parties in power has tended to leave them in a state of confusion, anger, and frustration because of the seemingly unending shift of goal posts where enforcement of the law is concerned. Besides, there are no advocacy groups to speak for them, largely because of the illegal nature of their business undertaking.

Source of Household (HH) Livelihood

Although street vending is illegal in Zambia, street vendors (SVs) claim that selling on the streets is their main source of household (HH) livelihood. One SV explained that “This is what we use to feed our children and our families at large; we want to make a profit, no matter how little it may be.” Another SV supported the argument of HH livelihood by adding that “the little we make helps us develop our lives and the livelihood of our families.” It is evident that although street vending is illegal in Zambia, many SVs engage in gainful informal jobs. According to the Labour Force Survey (2021), the Copperbelt unemployment rate stands at 18.7%, second only to Lusaka province at 23.3%, the highest. Arguably, it remains to be proved whether the street vending

informal jobs contribute significantly to the economic wellbeing of Zambia or not. Lessons can be drawn from other countries where street vending is regulated. The researchers are of the view that the central government, local authorities, and interested future researchers should consider undertaking exposure visits, especially to China, with a view to conducting a comparative study between regulating street vending and its potential economic benefits, as opposed to focusing only on its unlawful nature in Zambia. It is worth noting that the largest workers earn their living in the informal sector globally. For example, WIEGO (2024) argues that:

“61% of the world’s workers earn their living in the informal economy—in jobs and enterprises that are not regulated or protected by the government but that provide critical economic opportunities for the working poor. In these jobs, poverty rates are high and respect for human rights and workers’ rights is low (Women in Informal Employment: Globalizing and Organizing (WIEGO, 2024).”

Alleged Unreasonable Use of Force

It was found that at times, the law enforcement officers have allegedly applied unreasonable force to remove street vendors in Ndola Town, to the extent that injury and the unreported death of one street vendor occurred in 2023. One street vendor narrated that “someone was beaten up by law enforcement officers and died a few days later.” However, the researchers could not establish if the cause of death for this particular street vendor was indeed the beating he received, as this was outside the scope of the research. Nevertheless, this allegation from the street vendors is worth noting because it borders on a human rights violation. It is hoped that further investigations can be undertaken by the relevant authorities concerned. On the other hand, it was also reported by one of the LA officers that “some of the Local Authority Police Officers were also beaten up by street vendors due to an altercation they had.” In this incident, the LA officer disclosed that “all the street vendors involved in violence were arrested and charged.” The law is

clear on the use of reasonable force by any arresting officer on any person who forcibly resists such arrest or attempts to evade being arrested. In any case, it is the purview of the court to consider whether the means utilized by the arresting police officer were essential or the level of power utilized was sensible for the apprehension of such an individual, having respect to the gravity of the offense that had been, or alternately was being, committed by such an individual and the conditions in which such an offense had been, or alternately was being, committed by such an individual.

Allegations of Increase Forms of Corruption

Street vendors disclosed that there is an increase in the forms of corruption whenever law enforcement officers execute their operations in Ndola Town. These forms of corruption include bribery and abuse of authority, where the illegal acquisition of pecuniary resources by the aforementioned officers has been noticed. One street vendor even said, “Sometimes they collect bribes from us, and yet we haven’t even made proper sales.” Another street vendor added that “the way these methods are being done is not professional because they also take bribes from the same vendors in order to allow them to trade here, which again is solving nothing.” According to the Anti-Corruption Act No. 3 of 2012, corruption is defined as:

- Soliciting, accepting, obtaining, giving, promising, or offering gratification by way of a bribe or other personal temptation of inducement.
- Misuse or abuse of a public office for private advantage or benefit.

If law enforcement officers are allegedly taking bribes during their operations to remove street vendors from the streets, then it defeats the purpose of implementing the law on street vending.

Unfair Treatment

Most, if not all, of the street vendors interviewed expressed their frustrations with the manner in which the LA security officers implemented their mandate to remove them from the streets. The two major issues noted are the imposition of fines not receipted and the irrevocable seizure of their goods whenever LA security officers confiscate them. One street vendor disclosed that "sometime back they used to give trading permits; if they can re-introduce that, it would be better and maybe make a more modern market than the one that is already there, because taking our food is not necessary, and to make matters worse, they don't return our food back." LA officers have been accused of effecting double punishment by street vendors. We argue that although it is the purview of the courts of competent jurisdiction to enter an order on all the street vendors convicted, many are yet to be tried in the same courts.

Rationale for People Engaging in Street Vending

Some of the street vendors interviewed disclosed that selling on the streets is the easiest and fastest way to make a living. Furthermore, other street vendors lamented the lack of financial capacity to rent shops as well as the high cost of living as some of the reasons they opt to sell in the streets. Some of them disclosed that "it requires less start-up capital" to sell in the streets, and others argued that inadequate market spaces and a lack of market access to customers force them to sell in the streets. Street vendors want to strategically position themselves among pedestrians, who are potential customers. Street vending is "unregulated and hence provides quick access to the market," argued one of the street vendors. It was also found that some of the market spaces allocated to traders remain unutilized for some time, if not years. It is not clear whether the council earns revenue on a continuous basis from these traders with unutilized market spaces allocated to them. The local authority will do well to conduct a market space audit in all the registered markets in Ndola district.

Current Situation of Trading Spaces in the Markets (Registered and Unregistered)

Hygiene and Sanitary Facilities

The researchers noted that the street vendors come from different locations in Ndola Town and have information on the prevailing hygiene and sanitary conditions in the respective markets. Almost all the street vendors complained about poor hygiene and sanitary facilities in both registered and unregistered markets in Ndola. Some of the street vendors were quick to argue that poor hygiene and sanitary conditions forced them to trade in the streets. One participant disclosed that “The hygiene is not good and the way they were built is not up to standard and our customers are not always ready to come all the way to the market which means no sales, it is not located in a nice area.” It was also found that markets located near residential areas tend to have poor waste management, as most of the time, the garbage is not collected on time. It was also noted that this poor garbage collection challenge is largely caused by some households who dump their refuse in the night for fear of paying appropriate garbage collection fees. Furthermore, garbage bins fill up at a faster rate in markets where most of the vegetable sellers are largely dominant. This is in line with what Chileshe (2020) found in his study that street vending has been identified as an unsanitary practice that may have contributed to the 2017 cholera outbreak in Lusaka, Zambia, which was the latest in a string of outbreaks the country has seen.

Poor location of markets

The location of markets as well as market access by traders to potential buyers were found to be some of the major challenges facing traders and marketers in the markets. Street vendors complained of poorly located markets, and the design of the markets do not easily allow them to have easy access to potential passers-by buyers. In view of the traditional four (4) P's of marketing mix, "place," or location, is key if any business is to have access to potential buyers (Xia, 2023).

A business cannot exit and survive if it is poorly located. In this regard, street vendors opt to remain in the streets because passersby are not only potential customers for their goods but also buy from them as they find it convenient. By implication, street vendors defined market access as “public convenience service and quick sale” of their goods.

Photo 1

Vehicle Street Vending of dry fish and Kapenta

Suffice to argue that “public convenience and quick access to market” is one of the driving forces behind street vendors’ adamant position on their illegal vending. However, striking a balance between the vices of street vending, its illegal nature, and street vendors offering “public convenient service and quick access to market” is one area that can be considered by LA and policymakers as opposed to completely closing the door for dialogue and law reforms. It was observed during the interviews with street vendors that some of the prominent customers of street vendors include law enforcers themselves. The tension is that street vendors not only want market access but also the need to make quick sales, while the public want convenience and quick and easy access to goods and services despite been aware of the illegal nature of the business.

We argue by way of projection that as long as the general public continues to promote street vending because of convenience and easy market access, the efforts, strategies, and resources of the current and future governments will always not yield the desired outcomes. The questions that begs answering is: will the general public cease to buy from street vendors even if the penalties

of doing so are increased? Will the street vendors cease to abrogate the law with increasing levels of unemployment in the country?

Capacity of Markets

Some of the street vendors disclosed that the Chisokone Town Market is smaller than the Kapalala Market, which has over 2000 trading spaces. They were of the view that the opposite should have happened: Chisokone Market should have been bigger than Kapalala Market, located outside the Central Business District (CBD). One participant argued that “the markets are small and they cannot accommodate us that is why we have no option but to do street vending, and out here we have been making more than we do when we are in the markets.” It was also found that Mushili Market has a capacity of about 330 trading spaces.

In this regard, most of the street vendors have called for engineers to redesign all the markets to address the issue of market access for potential buyers who are passersby for all traders in the available markets. “If your stand in the market is poorly located where potential buyers cannot easily reach it, it is difficult to sell, and at times, you cannot even sell anything in a day,” said one street vendor interviewed. As if that were not enough, another street vendor lamented that “some traders in the markets use witchcraft charms to attract customers, and this tends to scare away other traders from the markets.” Some traders use vehicles to vend in the streets of Ndola especially the CBD.

Street Vending Eviction Approach

Shop owners in the CBD were interviewed on their views of the LA interventions to curb street vending in Ndola. The findings from shop owners were mixed. One of the shop owners was of the view that the LA plans to curb street vending do not yield the desired results because it is a “cat and mouse exercise”. Another shop owner argued that the intervention plans by LA to curb

street vending was inhuman and uncivilized because street vendors are beaten up to a point that one allegedly lost his life and others end up badly injured. Some shop owners also disclosed that the LA approach has led to corrupt activities where street vendors bribe them with money and goods to remain in the streets. Some LA officials are allegedly abusing their authority in the process and enrich themselves during the operation. However, other shop owners were of the view that LA's approach to remove and prevent street vending is a good approach. However, this particular shop owner was quick to add that LA needs to find a better approach to prevent street vendors to avoid loss of lives and injury.

Shop Owners' Views on LA Plans to Curb Street Vending

Some shop owners interviewed are of the view that the LA has not imposed stiffer punishment on street vendors when caught because of corruption. For example, one shop owner disclosed that "The way these methods are being done is not professional, because they also take bribes from the same vendors in order to allow them to trade here which again is solving nothing." Another shop owner added that "it is more corrupt and less of a solution, because these people often come to take their foods and products and do not return them," "how is that solving a problem?" Furthermore, implementation of LA plans to curb street vending has been described by other shop owners as ineffective. For example, one shop owner argued that "the positive way forward has not been found, it seems like we are going around in circles, because in the first place the council should have found a better place to take the vendors before chasing them, now they are promoting theft, street kids and poverty with the methods they are using and its quite evident they always have not been effective." It has been noted that the implementation of LA plans to curb street vending does not show any signs of providing a sustainable solution. For example, another shop owner argued that "the way they are implementing the methods is not very promising in terms of providing a long term solution to our problem." It has been argued by shop owners that removing

street vendors by force will not deter them from getting back to sell in the streets. Better approaches and enforcement of the law is needed. Furthermore, the shop owners have described the implementation of LA plans to remove street vendors from the CBD as unethically done and uncivilized. For example, one shop owner argued that “I don’t see it to be ethical, it is not humane although the council are civilized professionals.” Moreover, “...in as much as they are doing this for the good of the people, they must do it in an orderly non-violent manner.”

The argument is that, since time immemorial, street vendors have been chased from the streets but up to today they are still in the streets. It is rational to argue that the LA officials need to re-think their strategies and do it differently or still, the lawmakers must revisit the current law and amend it. LA should learn from other countries which have successfully allowed street vending without comprising on among other things including the security, hygiene and sanitary conditions.

Local Authority Plans to Curb Street Vending

The LA disclosed their intentions to relocate street vendors to Kapalala market which has capacity of over 2000 market spaces. In addition, the LA security Officers have been patrolling the CBD to ensure there are no street vendors. It was noted in one of the interviews with one LA official that, so far, the LA management has been commended for rendering unwavering support to law enforcers in the fight against street vending in terms of logistics. It was found that, there are no hygiene and sensitization programs targeting street vending. In this regard, LA officials have made proposals to engage in public sensitization programs to curb street vending. However, implementation of these plans by LA has not been without challenges. Most often than not, LA officials not only face resistance from street vendors, but also the public who find it convenient to buy from them. In addition, there have been times when the LA officials have been over-powered by street vendors because of limited capacity. In this regard, during the course of duty some LA officials have been beaten up by street vendors who were later arrested and charged. There have

been a number of accidents both by LA officials and street vendors during the crackdown operation. Some of the street vendors have devised other ways to continue abrogating the law, for example they wait until LA officials knock off to start selling, others display their goods immediately LA officials leave a particular area, others keep shifting places to sell in the effort to elude the LA officials, and others resorted to a confrontation approach. It was also noted that sometimes lack of political will and political interference in the past has rendered the LA efforts to remove street vendors from the streets not to yield the desired results. It is clear from the interviews conducted that LA officials expend a lot of resources and effort to remove street vendors from the streets despite the negative results achieved in the last few months in some streets of Ndola CBD. It is evident that management support and the will to enforce the law is there but for the resistant street vendors. A more professional and well thought-out win-win strategy is needed as opposed to only focusing on the enforcement of the law, if street vending challenge will be sustainably addressed. Zambia can learn from other countries that have successfully addressed this problem and contextualize the solutions.

Reasons for disregarding the Law

Photo 2

Street Vendors selling vegetables after a year of street vending crackdowns by LA in Chisokone area of Ndola CBD.

The LA officials disclosed that street vendors intentionally violate the current law on street vending for various reasons. For example, one LA official argued that “the general public promotes street vending because they buy from them due to convenience and easy market access.”

If street vending is to end in Zambia, the public should be sensitized to the dangers of street vending and stop buying from street vendors.

However, other LA officials were of the view that unfavorable economic conditions force people to engage in street vending. “Now days, others even sell their goods in their parked vehicles on the streets,” narrated one LA official. It was also found that the issue of market access by street vendors is also one of the major reasons people engage in street vending. For example, “street vending is the easiest way for the old-aged women to sell in the streets to provide for their families,” claimed one LA official. Furthermore, the population has grown, and the designs of the markets have not been updated to modern ones since the era of the first Republican president. Arguably, most often than not, traders opt to trade outside the markets in search of buyers because of poorly designed market structures,” claimed one LA official. This argument is in agreement with what the street vendors claimed.

It is without any doubt that the issue of redesigning market structures is key in the quest to address street vending in Ndola. Although the aforementioned reasons why people intentionally violate the law on street vending cannot be justified by supporting total disregard for the law and impunity, these are valid points that should not be ignored by policymakers and lawmakers. We argue that street vending is no longer undertaken by the poor and vulnerable people but also the educated and formally employed people.

Plans by ZEMA to Curb Environmental Pollution

An interview was conducted with one subject matter expert at the Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA). ZEMA is mandated by law to ensure the following plans are implemented effectively:

- Timely approval of the disposal of waste management sites.

- Technical guidance on the disposal of waste management site standards
- Provide approval conditions for Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs).

The official from ZEMA disclosed that street vendors generate what is known as municipal waste and fall under the LA mandate to address it. A perusal of the law indeed shows that ZEMA does not have direct jurisdiction over the management of municipal waste. The provisions of Solid Waste Regulation and Management Act No. 20 of 2018 in this case are instructive. Part II of the Act deals with the management of solid waste. Section 6 in particular is the section that provides for the control of solid waste by LAs. Notable findings from this interview included the need to have markets redesigned to accommodate population growth and also resolve the inability of all traders inside the markets to have equal market access to potential buyers. It was also noted that sometimes the LA is faced with inadequate provision of waste disposal bins to all markets and CBD. Furthermore, due to population growth, the town also needs to be redesigned to facilitate efficient market access points for goods and services. To address the challenge of street vending in Ndola, the ZEMA expert has recommended the following:

- Designate streets in the CBD for street vending for a certain period of the day or time.
- Provide adequate sanitary facilities in all market access points.
- Create bus stations near markets.
- Address the root cause of perpetual street vending as opposed to enforcing the law.

It is evident from the interview with the ZEMA expert that policy and law makers need to re-look at the current strategy and law to come up with a win-win formula to address perpetual street vending.

Paradoxical Tensions to Sustainable Panaceas for Street Vending

The respondents in this research expressed their mixed views on sustainable panaceas for street vending. We argue that there are paradoxical tensions to sustainable panaceas for street vending. Synthesis of the findings reviewed key sustainable solutions for and against street vending worth considering by policy and law makers urgently as follows:

Table 1

Sustainable Panaceas to Street Vending (SV) Arguments for and Against

	Argument for SV	Argument Against	Paradoxical tensions: Research gaps
1	Regulate street vending by: allocating a timeframe, give trading permits, consider a form of tax system for street vending, and reintroduce Hawkers licenses. -Win-win Approach	Political will is needed to sustain the efforts.	There is tension between regulating street vending due to high unemployment levels versus the political will to eliminate street vending.
2	Revisit the current law on SV.	The current law is adequate. Enforce the law. Stiffen the SV Penalties	There is tension between revisiting the current law to amend it versus enforcing the sufficient law.
3	Redesign Markets: Build big and modern markets in CBD.	Land in the CBD is depleted.	There is tension between building big modern markets in the CBD area versus no land available.
4	Although the LA has yet to come up with hygiene and sensitization programs, it was found that these programs are key to changing not only the mindset of street vendors but the general public at large.	Street vendors selling fruits and vegetables generate the highest municipal solid waste in Ndola.	There is tension between the promotions of hygiene programs versus the behavior of street vendors.
5	Re-design market structures to address access points and capacity.		
6	Build modern structures and more market spaces.	Markets have empty spaces. E.g., the Kapalala market with over 2,000 market spaces is not full.	Tension between markets with empty spaces versus building more markets.

7	Reducing Corruption through the Promotion of Ethical Conduct by Law Enforcers	LA to Re-Strategize its Street Vending Eviction Interventions	There is tension between reducing corruption versus allegations of LA officers enforcing engaging in corruption during street vending crackdowns.
8	Introduce mobile trading stands, e.g., Yatai of Japan.		
9	Allocate streets and time for street vending.	Poor hygiene, sanitation, and other vices that come with street vending	There is tension between regulating street vending and addressing the vices that result from it.
10	Improve sanitary facilities		
11	Build police posts near markets.		
12	Clean markets adequately		
13	Permanent temporariness of informal symbiotic business relationships between shop owners and street vendors for mutual benefits.	Enforcing the law against street vending.	The tension between dismantling the informal cartels between suppliers (e.g., shop owners) with street vendors versus lack of customers their products.

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents are for street vending in Ndola. However, to develop a win-win strategy, policymakers and lawmakers should consider resolving the eight paradoxical tensions highlighted in Table 1. Although the researchers did not in any way recommend a complete set of paradoxical tensions, the highlighted ones can be viewed as critical ones on the path to finding a lasting solution to street vending in Ndola. As long as these tensions continue to exist, the city will be divided on matters to do with street vending as the scripture puts it: “...Every kingdom divided against itself is brought to desolation, and every city or house divided against itself will not stand...”(Matthew 12:25b). Furthermore, investigations can be carried out by future researchers using quantitative research methodology on all the eight paradoxical tensions. As long as the impasse between these street vendors and the government exists, there will probably be no sustainable solution on street vending.

DISCUSSION

Arising from the key findings, there are discussion points that can foster dialogue with key stakeholders including the street vendors, shop owners, market managers, policymakers, LA officials and central government officials

Street vending contributes to boosting the economic activities of a particular economy through easy access to markets and the creation of informal employment for street vendors. For example, Du et. al. (2024) contends that the street vendor economy is a well-established and widely influential economic model in China and other developing nations. Although street vending as an economic model is not formalized in Zambia, it has significant potential to contribute to the growth of the economy because many players are involved. Street vending should not only be viewed in the context of the Zambian law where sellers sell in the undesignated sites but rather, it should also include those who sell via various online platforms such as meta (formerly facebook), whatsapp groups, Instagram, Telegram, TikTok, X (formerly Twitter), and also vendors who sell merchandise in their vehicles. The economic value of business transactions conducted on various online platforms in Zambia is also not known. On the contrary, there are also business trading risks involved on all the various social media platforms including cybercrimes. The Zambian government should therefore, re-consider this influential economic model and learn from countries like China and America (e.g. New York City) which have successfully formalized street vending.

There are paradoxical tensions to sustainable panaceas for street vending. As long as the impasse between these street vendors and the government exists, there will probably be no sustainable solution to street vending problem. This agrees with Njaya (2024) who argued that even though it's against the law to sell street food, doing so has greatly lowered unemployment, raised vendor earnings, and given urban residents access to affordable, diverse native meals in

Zimbabwe. The establishment of legislation and a code of conduct for street food vendors are two ways the government should acknowledge the street food business (Njaya, 2024).

Although there are several studies conducted on this subject globally, a gap exists on sustainable panaceas for street vending, contextualized to African countries. Many African countries focus on the enforcement of the law against street vending as opposed to formalizing it. In the process, the motivations of street vendors have not been considered by authorities because of the illegal nature of their business activity. Therefore, many African governments do not see the need to draw lessons from other countries on how to contextualize solutions for street vending. Ogunkola et. al. (2021) claimed that there has been reduced economic growth and increased hunger among individuals involved in street vending practices due to the prohibitions put in place by governments. Promoting inclusiveness in accessing public spaces without capturing informal actors such as street vendors is a missed opportunity in many African countries.

There are inconsistencies in the enforcement of the law by different political parties in power based on their development agenda.

- MMD Party-Focused on Liberalism/multi-partism.
- PF Party-Focused on Pro-poor policies.
- UPND Party-The focus is mainly: Economic reconstruction, diplomacy and expansion.

It is evident from the historical context of Zambia that each government in power has a different agenda for street vendors. This agrees with Chileshe (2020) who argued that A review of the literature reveals that street vending creates polarizing circumstances and sparks a great deal of debate. Furthermore, According to Resnick (2014), taxation is always political and especially so in Zambia where the Patriotic Front's slogan of 'more jobs, lower taxes, more money in your

pockets' resonated strongly among urban marketeers and street vendors during the multiple electoral campaigns under the late president, Michael Sata.

Although it is the purview of the courts of competent jurisdiction in Zambia to enter an order on all the street vendors convicted, many are yet to be tried in the same courts. In many cases, street vendors are not tried before the courts of competent jurisdiction when caught selling in the streets. Although fines are paid, their goods are seized and in most cases they are not given receipts and there are no advocacy groups to champion their cause. Besides, despite the local authorities having on several occasions removed street vendors from trading in the streets, the exercise has not yielded the desired results over time. This unsuccessful eviction operations in most cases is largely attributed to what the street vendors and shop owners have described as “Cat and Mouse” approach. Street vendors keep going back to sell in the same and in some cases shift to other streets to evade the LA security officers. For example, the Lusaka City Council in Zambia, has maintained that it can only be successful in managing vendors if all city dwellers cease purchasing food and non-food items from vendors and also lend support to council police personnel (Lusaka Times, November 4, 2018). Residents of Lusaka, however, seem to have ignored this plea, since they have kept purchasing goods from the street vendors (Chileshe, 2020).

Street vending is no longer undertaken by the poor, uneducated, and vulnerable people but also the educated and formally employed people because of deteriorating economic conditions. For example ‘Vehicle Street Vending’ i.e. street vending using vehicles (vans) is on the rise and causing congestion in the CBD of Ndola Town. The Zambian government can learn from the USA on how to regulate food vans. For example, In 2015, the US city of Albuquerque explored enacting a new law that would have prevented food trucks with vending machines from operating within 30 meters of eateries that were already established, unless the owners of the properties specifically gave their consent (Ehrenfeucht, 2016).

Sustainable Solutions: Participants views

Study participants were of the view that dialogue needs to be promoted in the absence of advocacy groups for street vendors in the following ways:

1. **Formalize Street Vending:** Government to put in place measures to formalize street vending because of the high levels of unemployment. See table 2 unemployment statistics.

Table 2

Unemployment Statistics

No.	Description	Rate (%)	Source
1	Copperbelt unemployment	18.7%	Labour Force Survey (2021)
2	Country level unemployment	68.5%	ZAMSTATS (2024)
3	Sub-Saharan Africa size of Informal sector	72.0%	ILO (2018)
4	Global size of informal sector	60.0%	ILO (2018)
5	Informal economy	63.5%	ILO (2018)

2. **Re-Strategize:** Develop a “win-win” and not “cat and mouse” strategy.
3. **Consistent law enforcement:** Different political parties that come into government must be consistent with the law.
4. **Stop double punishment:** Stop seizing goods where a ransom payment was made.
5. **Inclusivity in accessing public spaces:** The LA to put in place measures of how street vendors can access public spaces because they have a right to do so.

6. ***Consider the motivations of street vendors:*** The LA should seek to understand the motivations of street vendors to come up with a lasting solution.
7. ***Quick and convenient market access:*** Quick and convenient access to goods is what motivates the public to keep buying from street vendors, which defeats the efforts of LA.
8. ***The educated and formally employed people:*** Street vending is no longer undertaken by the poor, uneducated, and vulnerable people but also the educated and formally employed people because of because of deteriorating economic conditions. Therefore, the government needs to consider formalizing street vending.

CONCLUSION

Despite the efforts and resources expended by the Local Authority in Ndola, street vending is still a big challenge. The Local Authority should change its strategy and find a sustainable solution. We are of a considered view that a “win-win” rather than a “cat and mouse” strategy be implemented by the Local Authority because of the unfavorable economic conditions. Dialogue should also be encouraged that can culminate into law reforms to enhance justice and efficiency in the delivery of legally approved goods by all vendors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The central government and the LA need to consistently enforce the law. However, this research has found that amending the law to find a win-win strategy is a better option than enforcing the current law. Besides, there are valid economic reasons why street vendors engage in the informal sector to sell in the streets that academicians, policymakers, and other interested parties need to further conduct research on. Policymakers should also evaluate the economic value of street vending in the informal sector of Zambia. However, the questions that beg answers are: Does the informal sector contribute significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Zambia? If yes, what is the monetary value of street vending if it were to be legalized? The LA security department should encourage their officers to exercise maximum restraint and operate within the confines of the law during their street vending operations. The LA security department should also encourage their officers to exercise professionalism and refrain from engaging in alleged corrupt activities during their street vending operations. The LA Security officers who have been executing the mandate to remove street vendors from the streets should restrain from implementing double punishment where street vendors' goods are confiscated and not returned to them even after they pay the required fines. LA needs to improve hygiene and sanitary facilities in both registered and unregistered markets in Ndola. LA engineers need to consider redesigning the markets to meet modern demands. LA should consider undertaking a study to increase market spaces in view of the projected population growth in the different areas of Ndola District. The street vending deterrence approach by LA should be re-considered to become effective. Chasing street vendors time and again has been viewed by the respondents interviewed as a "cat and mouse" strategy and not sustainable. Due to decreasing public confidence in the current LA street vending operations, LA should consider re-strategizing its operations to find effective ways to execute its mandate. LA policymakers and lawmakers should consider a wide range of sustainable panaceas for street vending, as highlighted in this research article. To address perpetual street vending, the focus

should be more on resolving the eight paradoxical tensions highlighted in this research. In view of the various valid reasons for street vendors engaging in this business, there is a need for dialogue between policymakers and lawmakers to find a lasting solution.

AREAS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

- 1. Strategic focus:** Future researchers to focus on how to craft a “win-win” strategy as opposed to the current “cat and mouse” approach to controlling street vending.
- 2. Value for money analysis:** Future researchers conduct a cost-benefit analysis of LA crackdowns versus the outcomes achieved.
- 3. Law reforms:** Future researchers to specifically focus on an analysis of the current law on street vending to determine the possibility of street vendors offering “public convenience and quick access” to goods.
- 4. Market audit:** Conduct Market audits of spaces (utilized and unutilized) in all the registered and unregistered markets in Ndola to determine the availability of trading spaces.
- 5. Exposure visits:** Consider undertaking exposure visits to other countries that have formalized street vending and draw lessons.
- 6. Paradoxical tensions:** Future researchers investigate the best approach to addressing paradoxical tensions.

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